

Mind Over Wheels – Smart Wheel Chair with an Alert and Disinfection System Using AI

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Abstract -This paper presents an endemic-built hand-free wheelchair for disabled persons. Physically disabled and mentally disabled people like a person who is suffering from paralysis face difficulties in daily life because of their body impairment from their birth or due to an accident or some illness. The proposed system is based on a Head Motion Recognition technique using a MEMS Sensor (Acceleration Sensor). Conventional physical wheelchairs are generally powered by joysticks or hand gesture devices that can not address the needs of almost entirely disabled people who have limited limb movements and can barely move or turn their heads. The MEMS sensor is used for head gesture recognition and the NRF24L01 TX module is used for smart wireless control. Through the adjustment of the head motion, the information goes wirelessly to the Arduino Nano-dependent motor driving circuit to control the rotation of the Wheel Chair in four different modes, including FRONT, BACK, RIGHT, and LEFT. The goal is to design a wheelchair that could function for a disabled person who cannot move other parts of the body correctly, keeping their words in mind with the help of head movements. The prototype of the wheelchair performs head motion through an Arduino Nano. The DC motors will drive the wheelchair during the gesture of control mode. The motors will not work, and consequently, the wheelchair will not run when the head is neutral, and only when there is head movement the wheelchair will automatically move. A head motion-controlled wheelchair is an intelligent wheelchair with facilities for navigating, recognizing obstacles, and moving automatically by managing detectors and motions.

Keywords - AI-based wheelchair, Alert system, Disinfection system, Mobility assistance, Assistive technology.

1. INTRODUCTION

A Human being has been revered with the immunity to work and think independently. But there is a certain amount of people in the world who are being dispossessed from this privilege. Many people around the world are suffering from physical and mental disability. Disability is a continuing condition that restricts everyday activities freely. Around 10% of the world's population, or roughly 650 million people are affected by physical impairment. In most of the OECD countries, females have higher disability rates than males. Disability can be different types such as defective body parts, near-sightedness, limited hearing capacity, deafness, Intellectual disability, Blindness etc. In these circumstances, the disabled people need assistance of some instruments or need a helper to move from one to another place. John Dawson from England first designed a wheelchair in 1783 and George Klein invented the first power wheelchair for quadriplegia injured people in World War II. Over the years, there have been few improvements of some specific mobility's apparatus. Presently, mobility's materials such as wheelchairs and crutches are traditionally used by the disabled people. Many research works have been come out with evolving various ceremonial solutions. such as joystick-controlled wheelchair, Hand gesture, Android controlled wheelchair. But these are not enough for limiting the problem where the disabled people cannot perform task like normal people. In such case, a smart wheelchair can accommodate impaired people with better manner of movement. Head gesture navigation is a fanatical arrangement by which a disabled person can enjoy easy movement using only his head. The system is supplementary for those who lack of many body parts. Obstacle detector is helpful for blind people. And it also helps for all disabled peoples not only for the mentally disabled persons.

II. OBJECTIVE

Introducing an ingenious at the intersection of technology and accessibility: the AI-based wheelchair equipped with head gesture control, alert systems, and an integrated disinfection mechanism. This cutting-edge solution is designed to revolutionize mobility for individuals with limited motor function, ensuring not only seamless movement but also health and safety management. Imagine a wheelchair that understands and responds to a person's head gestures, empowering users to navigate effortlessly through their surroundings. By harnessing the power of artificial intelligence, this wheelchair Analyzes head movements, allowing users to guide, stop, and artifice with remarkable carefree precision. But that's not all. This advanced futuristic wheelchair goes beyond basic functionality. It incorporates an intelligent alert system that enhances safety by detecting obstacles, notifying the user, and impulsive adjusting the wheelchair's path to prevent collisions. Moreover, in today's health-conscious world, hygiene is preponderant. This AI-based wheelchair integrates a state-of-the-art disinfection system, ensuring a clean and sanitized environment for the user. Utilizing advanced technology, it autonomously sanitizes surfaces, minimizing the risk of infections and promoting a healthier environment for everyone. This innovative blend of AI-driven control, safety alerts, and proactive disinfection not only represents a leap forward in mobility assistance but also showcases the potential of technology to enhance the quality of life for individuals with diverse needs. With this AI-based wheelchair, we're not just redefining mobility; we're empowering independence, safety, and hygiene, fostering a world where technology serves as a catalyst for inclusivity and well-being.

Aim of the Work

The purpose of this work is to integrate a state-of-the art disinfection system. It automatically sanitizes surfaces, ensuring a clean and germ-free environment for the user, minimizing the risk of infections and promoting wellness. This groundbreaking innovation not only redefines mobility but also composes accessibility, safety, and health. It represents a fusion of technology and compassion, empowering individuals with limited mobility to navigate the world with confidence, comfort, and peace of mind. Moreover, in an era where cleanliness and hygiene are of utmost importance, this wheelchair doesn't just facilitate mobility it actively contributes to maintaining a sanitized environment. Enclosed with a smart disinfection system, it continuously sterilizes surfaces, reducing the risk of infectious agent and providing users with peace of mind. By combining these features, this AI-based wheelchair not only redefines mobility for individuals but also addresses their health and safety concerns, promoting a more inclusive and hygienic experience.

III. METHODOLOGY

The core idea for this Mind Over Wheels is physically impaired people can easily operate this wheel chair without any person's assistance. The system used in this Mind Over Wheels is split into two parts. One is a transmitting hand and the other is a receiver. The section of transmitter will be placed in the head band and the section of receiver well be placed in the wheelchair.

Fig 1: Section of Transmitter

The figure 1, shows the transmitter side consists primarily of three parts Arduino Nano, a MEMS sensor, and a NRF24L01 transmitter. In this wheelchair, we control the forward, backward, left, and right movement of the wheelchair. We are using a MEMS sensor to detect the motion of the head. Based on the person's requirement they can simply change the position of the head. The head motion will be detected by the sensor and these signals will be sent to Arduino Nano and then it will be sent to the receiver through the NRF24L01 transmitter.

Fig 2: Section of Receiver

Figure 2, it shows the receiver side which consists of NRF24L01 receiver, ultrasonic sensor, Arduino Uno, motor driver, buzzer and motors. Here Arduino is the heart of the project, based on the sensor data Arduino is going to control the chair. The signal will be received through NRF24L01 receiver from the transmitter. And then signal will be send to the Arduino Uno after processing it will be sent to motor. From the motor driver signal will be sent to the motors. The processor must take the decision because it is pre-programmed to monitor both the motor and the wheelchair route. Motor 1 and Motor 2 was added to explain the course of change in direction. Ultrasonic sensor is used to detect the obstacle, if any obstacle detected then buzzer will activate and gives the beep sound through the buzzer.

Figure 3: Proposed work flow

When the patient is seated in the wheelchair and wears the headband. First, it checks the motion of the head, if movement is detected then the signal is sent from the transmitter to the receiver of the NRF24L01 module. The received signal will be rechecked and processed the signal, if not the signal will be sent back to the transmitter. Only when the received signal is proper, the chair will move in the required direction. Suppose if any obstacle is detected the wheelchair will be stopped.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The head gesture control wheelchair project represents a significant advancement in assistive technology aimed at enhancing the mobility and independence of individuals with physical disabilities. Through the integration of innovative head gesture recognition technology with wheelchair controls, this project has successfully

demonstrated the feasibility and effectiveness of controlling a wheelchair using simple head movements. One of the primary conclusions drawn from this project is the potential of head gesture control systems to offer a viable alternative to traditional joystick-based control mechanisms. By harnessing the natural movements of the user's head, such systems can provide a more intuitive and ergonomic method of navigation, particularly for individuals with limited dexterity or mobility in their hands. This not only promotes greater autonomy and freedom of movement but also reduces the physical strain associated with operating conventional wheelchair controls, thereby enhancing user comfort and convenience. Furthermore, the development and implementation of the head gesture control system have underscored the importance of personalized and adaptive technology solutions in the field of assistive robotics. Through extensive user testing and feedback iterations, the project has highlighted the significance of tailoring the system to individual user needs and preferences, ensuring optimal usability and user experience. This emphasis on customization and user-centered design principles has paved the way for more inclusive and user-friendly assistive technologies, capable of catering to a diverse range of user abilities and requirements. Additionally, the successful deployment of the head gesture control wheelchair prototype underscores the potential for broader applications of gesture recognition technology in assistive robotics and beyond. Beyond wheelchair navigation, similar systems could be adapted for controlling other mobility aids, as well as for interfacing with smart home devices, computers, and other digital interfaces. This opens up exciting possibilities for enhancing accessibility and autonomy across various domains, empowering individuals with disabilities to fully participate in everyday activities and live more fulfilling lives. In conclusion, the head gesture control wheelchair project represents a significant step forward in the ongoing pursuit of innovative assistive technologies. By leveraging the power of head gesture recognition technology, this project has demonstrated the feasibility of intuitive and ergonomic wheelchair control systems, while also highlighting the importance of personalized, user-centered design approaches. Moving forward, continued research and development in this field hold the potential to further enhance the quality of life and independence of individuals with disabilities, ushering in a new era of inclusive and empowering assistive technologies.

V. ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

Advantages:

1. **Increased Mobility:** Individuals with limited mobility can navigate their environment more independently, enhancing their quality of life.
2. **Improved Safety:** AI can help anticipate obstacles and adjust wheelchair movements accordingly, reducing the risk of accidents.
3. **Customization:** AI algorithms can adapt to the user's behavior and preferences, providing personalized assistance.
4. **Hands-Free Operation:** Users can operate the wheelchair without the need for manual controls, freeing up their hands for other tasks.
5. **Integration with Smart Devices:** Integration with AI allows for seamless interaction with other smart devices and environments, enhancing overall accessibility.

Disadvantages:

1. **Complexity and Reliability:** The technology may be complex and require frequent maintenance, leading to potential reliability issues.
2. **Learning Curve:** Users and caregivers may require training to effectively operate and troubleshoot the system, which could be time-consuming.
3. **Cost:** Initial setup costs and ongoing maintenance expenses can be significant, limiting access for some individuals.
4. **Privacy and Security Concerns:** Brain-controlled systems raise privacy and security concerns related to the collection and use of sensitive neural data.
5. **Dependency on Technology:** Overreliance on AI-driven control may diminish users' ability to independently navigate in non-automated environments, potentially limiting their skills and confidence.

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